

1 **A PIECE OF THE ECOTOXICOLOGY PUZZLE: HOW CAN CURRENT AND FUTURE**
2 **RESEARCH INFORM PPD REGULATIONS?**

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48 Abstract

49 2-((4-Methylpentan-2-yl)amino)-5-(phenylamino)cyclohexa-2,5-diene-1,4-dione commonly
50 known as 6PPD-Quinone (6PPD-Q), is the ozonized derivative of, N-(1,3-dimethylbutyl)-N'-
51 phenyl-p-phenylenediamine, 6PPD. 6PPD is a common tire coating that prevents rubber
52 degradation by acting as an antioxidant. Research efforts elucidating 6PPD-Q's toxicity surged
53 after a 2021 study identified 6PPD-Q as an acute mortality inducing toxicant to coho salmon.
54 This commentary functions as a compilation of 6PPD and 6PPD-Q's interaction with aquatic and
55 terrestrial organisms. We also encompass studies providing toxicological explanations of
56 dysregulation of intracellular activity and metabolite transformation. We aim to concurrently
57 impart an overview of the most current 6PPD and 6PPD-Q studies at organismal and cellular
58 levels, emphasize research gaps, such as the lack of global regulations, and propose possible
59 routes for future studies, like the expansion into different model organisms, lifecycle effects,
60 fertility and transgenerational effects, and cancer cell studies.

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62 1. Introduction

63 For years, freshwater environments have been experiencing "urban stream syndrome," a
64 phenomenon attributed to the increased environmental pollutants altering water quality.¹ In
65 urbanized areas, road runoff is a contributing factor to the decline in freshwater habitats. Pacific
66 salmon, specifically coho salmon, are integral to the diverse connection between saltwater and
67 freshwater food webs.² However, coho salmon have been experiencing acute mortality rates
68 when migrating to freshwater ecosystems to reproduce. In 2021, N-(1,3-dimethylbutyl)-N'-
69 phenyl-p-phenylenediamine-quinone, 6PPD-Quinone (6PPD-Q), was identified as the main
70 contributor to the acute mortality rate seen in coho salmon.³
71 While this revelation is recent, its precursor 6PPD, was originally discovered in the 1960s. 6PPD
72 falls within a class of compounds called p-phenylenediamine (PPD) which are used as
73 antiozonant coatings on rubber tires to prevent breakdown and prolong usage.⁴ Since then,
74 there have been no alternative antiozonants that match 6PPD's ability to prevent rubber
75 breakdown.

76 As such, 6PPD has become a prominent environmental pollutant in recent years. When
77 entering the environment, 6PPD can react with ozone creating 6PPD-Q (Figure 1).⁵ Quinones,
78 when introduced *in vivo*, can induce cytotoxicity, immunotoxicity, or activate detoxification
79 enzymes, depending on their reactivity.⁶ Both molecules are ubiquitous and readily enter the
80 environment through road run-off, rubber waste, and dust, accumulating in both rural and urban
81 waterways (Supplemental Figure 1 and Supplemental Table 1). The half-life of 6PPD is
82 approximately 5 hours in water compared to 6PPD-Q which has a half-life of about 33 hours.⁷
83 Although the half-lives of both chemicals are relatively short, the amount of tires on the road at
84 any given time contribute to the continual leaching of PPDs into waterways. Additionally, even
85 small amounts of PPDs, in the ng/L range, can lead to mortality among aquatic wildlife. This
86 indicates high reactivity. Thus, continued usage of 6PPD and 6PPD-Q has raised concern for
87 aquatic life subjected to these chemicals.

88 Coho salmon seem to be more sensitive to PPDs unlike other freshwater species. The
89 coho salmon mortality discovery has opened the door to a new field in ecotoxicology research.
90 More publications starting in 2021 have revealed species, like zebrafish, with higher tolerances
91 to 6PPD and 6PPD-Q.⁷⁻¹⁸ Additionally, other species and *in vitro* models like *Caenorhabditis*

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99 *elegans* (*C. elegans*), when exposed to PPDs, have exhibited metabolic changes and
 100 dysregulated genes.^{4,10,19-23} Studies investigating PPD exposure in humans, starting in 2024,
 101 reported potential health impacts to those living in areas with high rubber recycling.^{19,20,24-26}
 102 Though impacts of 6PPD and 6PPD-Q are widespread, there are no global regulations
 103 against PPD usage. The United States Environmental Protection Agency, USEPA, is supplying
 104 funding to expand the understanding of 6PPD and 6PPD-Q's impact and has developed an
 105 action plan to mitigate the risks.^{27,28} The United States has completed initial aquatic life
 106 screenings to discern the acute exposure levels for 6PPD and 6PPD-Q, 8.9 µg/L and 11 ng/L,
 107 respectively.^{29,30} Comparatively, the Canadian Environmental Protection Agency, CEPA, has
 108 added PPDs to their substance priority list and are working towards possibly implementing a
 109 ban.³¹ The European Union's Registration, Evaluation, Authorisation and Restriction of
 110 Chemicals, REACH, is also considering employing restrictions of 6PPD use.³² Whichever
 111 country or region can amass sufficient research to support and implement their own regulations
 112 will likely help direct other global regulations.

113 Other PPD reviews and commentaries have been published covering environmental
 114 impacts on individual species. However this commentary aims to summarize what has been
 115 published thus far about the toxic effects of 6PPD and 6PPD-Q in multiple aquatic organisms,
 116 model organisms, and human cell lines since their discovery in coho salmon. To aid in
 117 comparison between species and cell lines, conversions of environmental concentrations (µg/L)
 118 of 6PPD and 6PPD-Q to molar concentrations are provided for reference (Supplemental Table
 119 2). We aim to point out the gaps occurring within the 6PPD and 6PPD-Q research domain and
 120 provide suggestions to drive scientific discovery, understanding, and regulations. Our
 121 recommendations include, transgenerational studies with a subfocus on epigenetics,
 122 toxicological impacts on female model organisms, implementation of fungal models, fate of PPD
 123 metabolites, toxicity to cancer cells, single cell sequencing, and coexposure of environmental
 124 toxicants.

125 Figure 1. Transformation of 6PPD to 6PPD-Q in the presence of ozone (O₃) (created using
 126 BioRender.com).

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Figure 2. Timeline of 6PPD and 6PPD-Q development, implementation, and toxic nature (created using [BioRender.com](#)).

2. Methods

To gather data, we used the National Library of Medicine (NIH) search engine PubMed. For example, we used keywords, 6PPD, 6PPD-Q, zebrafish, coho salmon, and *Caenorhabditis elegans* to identify how many papers had been published within this field of study. To further narrow our search, we included combinations of keywords into our searches such as “6PPD, zebrafish.” We then sorted through each paper to determine which area of study the paper focused on and if the information fit into the focus of our manuscript. We were unable to employ any time restrictions to our searches because all relevant research has been published within the last five years. Any paper published and available through PubMed was considered for our commentary.

3. Aquatic Organisms 3.1 Coho Salmon (*Oncorhynchus kisutch*)

Many efforts have been made to thoroughly investigate the consequences of environmental pollutant 6PPD-Q on coho salmon. Coho salmon are of high ecological importance because of well-documented “coho pre-spawn mortality” of adult coho salmon returning to spawn. We believe current findings indicate that even within species, the tolerance level of 6PPD-Q varies depending on life stage (Table 1). This presents the need to continually implement the assessment of species' progressional life stages into toxicology studies. Investigating embryo tolerance compared to adult coho salmon revealed significant mortality which occurred at 7.22 µg/L while adults experienced acute mortality at 1.2 to 1.8 µg/L.^{5,33} Though the adults appear to have decreased tolerance to 6PPD-Q, the variation between the two studies extend beyond the life stage and into experimental design and study objectives. Furthermore, we believe the discrepancy in reported tolerance values of juvenile coho salmon could also be due to contrasts in

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Deleted: Figure 12. Transformation of 6PPD to 6PPD-Q in the presence of ozone (O₃) (created using [BioRender.com](#)).[†]

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Deleted: To what extent are coho salmon (*Oncorhynchus kisutch*) affected by 6PPD-Q? [†]

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173 study design. One study reported juvenile lethal concentrations (LC50) as an average of
174 $0.79 \pm 0.16 \mu\text{g/L}$ after only 2 to 6 hours of exposure whereas another study found a
175 constant 24 exposure decreased the median LC50 to 41.0 ng/L .^{3,34} Confirming lethal
176 concentrations for embryonic to adult populations will help inform regulations and
177 preserve sensitive species' populations. **3.2 Zebrafish (*Danio rerio*)** Since the
178 discovery of 6PPD-Q toxicity in coho salmon, research has shifted to using zebrafish embryos
179 and larvae when investigating the effects of environmental levels of 6PPD and 6PPD-Q. The
180 catalyst for the shift being a comparison between the similar life stages. Their short gestational
181 times and transparent bodies make morphological studies simple and accessible. Evidence thus
182 far has categorized zebrafish as a more "tolerant" species.¹⁶ As new studies are published, the
183 effects of PPDs seem to extend beyond mortality and into morphological, behavioral, and
184 physiological changes.

3.3 Zebrafish Mortality

185 Since zebrafish LC50 values vary so greatly depending on methodology, the definitive
186 categorization of zebrafish may be more nuanced than strictly "tolerant." We find, like the coho
187 salmon studies, the experimental design, data acquisition, and analysis in zebrafish studies
188 makes comparing LC50 values difficult. One study reported the estimated LC50 value for 6PPD
189 to be $442.62 \mu\text{g/L}$ and $132.92 \mu\text{g/L}$ for 6PPD-Q after 96 hours of maintained exposure.⁸
190 Alternatively, after 120 hours of stable exposure the measured LC50 value for 6PPD increased
191 to 0.87 mg/L and no effect was found in zebrafish embryos exposed to 6PPD-Q up to 10
192 mg/L .¹⁸ This evidence further highlights the difficulty of comparing mortality rates between and
193 within species.

3.4 Zebrafish Morphology

194 Multiple studies have also observed morphological alterations in zebrafish. Variable
195 6PPD concentrations resulted in decreases in eye development and eye size, hatchability, body
196 length, and swim bladder size.^{8,10,13,14,18} Comparatively, zebrafish exposed to a range of 6PPD-
197 Q concentrations, had no significant changes to bladder development. However, zebrafish had
198 increased instances of reduced eye size, lordosis, kyphosis, and malformations of the tail.^{8,14,18}
199 While decrease in eye size is consistent between both chemicals, other morphological effects
200 indicate a difference in 6PPD and 6PPD-Q's biological targets.

3.5 Zebrafish Behavior and Physiology

201 Along with morphological changes, PPDs also altered zebrafish behavior and
202 physiological conditions. A cardiovascular trend was seen when investigating the physiological
203 effects of 6PPD-Q at $10\text{-}25 \mu\text{g/L}$ and $20\text{-}2000 \text{ ng/L}$ respectively. Both discovered 6PPD-Q was
204 linked to cardiotoxicity by way of altered heart rate (BPM).^{8,16} A trend in swim behavior was also
205 seen in both studies as one reported decreases in swim velocity and the other saw reduced
206 locomotive activity.^{8,16} Two studies treated zebrafish larvae with both PPDs for 120 hours and
207 reported behavioral changes. 0.4 mg/L 6PPD was found to inhibit phototactic behavior while 50
208 $\mu\text{g/L}$ of 6PPD-Q was associated with decreased swim distance.^{10,18} After evaluating the
209 presented evidence, we believe it is possible that PPDs interfere with normal swimming
210 behavior typically seen in healthy zebrafish larvae.

4. Terrestrial Organisms

4.1 Mice (*Mus musculus*)

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338 Toxic effects of 6PPD-Q have also started to be studied in mammalian models such as
339 male mice. Male mice offer a good fertility model because of their short reproductive times.
340 Across many studies, 6PPD-Q has been found to complicate reproductive processes and
341 induce inflammation responses).³⁵⁻⁴¹ However, there is still a major research gap including
342 female mice models. Because of the wide effects of 6PPD-Q seen in other model organisms as
343 well as male mice, additional studies focusing on female mice models would improve our
344 understanding of the toxic mechanisms of PPDs.

345 The male mice studies have mainly found negative effects in fertility, the inflammatory
346 response, and liver disease. In one study, when injected with 4 mg/kg 6PPD-Q, mouse
347 testosterone levels decreased and sperm quality declined. This led to complications in *in vitro*
348 fertilization (IVF) and suggested impaired male fertility.⁴⁰ Additionally, pathways involving
349 spermatogenesis and sphingolipid metabolism were differentially affected.⁴⁰

350 Furthermore, multiple studies observed fluctuations in inflammation responses. Two
351 studies employed different methods of 6PPD-Q exposure on two mouse models. The
352 first injected 10 and 100 µg/kg for 21 days and the second injected one dose of 4 mg/kg
353 and monitored response over one week. Both saw an increase in the inflammatory
354 cytokines, TNF-α, IL-1, IL-6, and IL-10.^{36,37} A third study injected mice with 0.4 and 4
355 mg/kg 6PPD-Q every 4 days for a 28 day period and saw similar increases in
356 inflammatory cytokines. They also discovered increased instances of apoptosis, blood-
357 brain barrier disruption, and increased levels of reactive oxygen species (ROS).³⁸ 6PPD-
358 Q has also been found to contribute to hepatotoxicity in mice. Long term exposure for 21
359 days via the oral route, (0.1 and 1 µg/kg bw per day) led to elevated lipid deposition in
360 the liver which can contribute to metabolic dysfunction-associated steatotic liver disease
361 (MASLD).³⁹ These selected mice studies highlight the various toxic effects of 6PPD-Q.

362 4.2 Humans (*Homo sapiens*)

363 Currently, there are no regulations for acceptable daily intake (ADI) or tolerable daily
364 intake (TDI) for PPDs. More studies encompassing dust exposure, human excretions, co-
365 exposure with other toxicants, and transgenerational transmission will give greater insight on
366 exposure level so tolerance can be established. To better understand the effects of 6PPD and
367 its quinone derivative on human health populations, epidemiology studies were carried out in
368 areas with high electronic and rubber waste disposal. In industrialized China, children from ages
369 2 to 7 underwent urine analysis to detect PPDs and results were compared to a control group
370 located farther from the waste disposal site. The median levels of PPDs, 6PPD 0.073 and
371 6PPD-Q 2.34 ng/mL, were reportedly higher for the group in closer proximity to the waste
372 plant.²⁴ Also, dust samples from houses, kindergartens, and road areas with high levels of
373 rubber recycling were compared to a control. For houses and kindergartens, the concentration of
374 6PPD-Q was higher, 3.2 and 7.5 ng/g, respectively.²⁶ The same study also investigated the
375 presence of polybrominated diphenyl ethers (PBDEs), polychlorinated biphenyls (PCBs), and
376 heavy metal(loid)s, (Ni and Cu) in kindergarten dust samples. The combination of multitoxicant
377 exposure is thought to be further associated with a decrease in body mass index (BMI),
378 alteration of the gut microbiota, and more frequent illnesses such as influenza, in areas with
379 high rubber recycling.^{25,26} Ingestion of dust in toddlers, approximately 3.48 ng/kg bw/d, was
380 suspected to be linked to indoor venues through paint and flooring materials.¹⁹ Although the
381 main focus this far has been on PPDs effects in children, one study detected the toxicants in

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Deleted: There is still a major research gap including female mice as well as exposure to 6PPD. Because of the wide effects of 6PPD-Q, additional studies focusing on these areas would improve our understanding of the toxic mechanisms of both PPDs allowing for better informed policy and regulations.¹

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396 breastmilk and adult urine.²⁰ These findings may indicate a possible passage of PPDs and other
397 toxicants from parent to child. Additionally, the showcased studies highlight the presence of both
398 PPDs in areas with high concentrations of rubber recycling and possible interactions with other
399 environmental toxicants.

400 4.3 *Caenorhabditis elegans* (*C. elegans*)

401 While 6PPD-Q is often confirmed to be in freshwater environments, it has also been
402 found in dirt and air samples. 6PPD-Q has been reported to have many negative effects, which
403 is why moving forward *Caenorhabditis elegans* (*C. elegans*) provide a novel avenue to help
404 further understanding of the toxicants biological targets and allow for better informed
405 regulations. *C. elegans* offer unique insight upon 6PPD-Q exposure as they are terrestrial, but
406 can appear in aquatic environments.

407 Unlike zebrafish, *C. elegans* do not appear to exhibit drastic changes to morphology or
408 mortality upon 6PPD-Q exposure. Investigating mortality in nematodes revealed only a 5
409 percent mortality rate when subjected to 100 µg/L 6PPD-Q. Though mortality is uncommon in *C.*
410 *elegans*, three studies found 6PPD-Q exposure resulted in a decreased lifespan.⁴²⁻⁴⁵

411 Consistent with zebrafish, 6PPD-Q exposure was linked to behavioral changes in *C.*
412 *elegans*. Two studies found treatment of lower 6PPD-Q concentrations, ranging from 0.1 to 10
413 µg/L, resulted in decreased abnormal locomotion. This was hypothesized to be associated with
414 the neurodegeneration observed in D-type neurons.^{46,47} Neurodegeneration was also observed
415 in dopaminergic, glutamatergic, serotonergic, and GABAergic neurons resulting in decreased
416 sensory perception and neurotransmission.⁴⁶ Comparatively, exposure to 1 to 10 µg/L 6PPD-Q
417 resulted in a decrease of dopamine synthesis leading to a decline in dopamine related
418 behavior.⁴⁷ These studies highlight that 6PPD-Q seems to be a neurotoxin, targeting a multitude
419 of neurons and inhibiting normal behavior.

420 Physiological alterations were also apparent in nematodes, though the processes
421 affected were different than those in zebrafish. Increased intestinal permeability was found in
422 nematodes exposed to 1 to 10 µg/L 6-PPD-Q.^{42,47,48} Metabolism appears to be broadly affected
423 as an increase in fatty acid synthesis resulted in lipid accumulation. Glycogen and glucose
424 metabolism were also inversely affected as 6PPD-Q exposure resulted in an increase of
425 glycogen metabolism and a decrease of glucose metabolism.^{43,45,49,50} Each of these responses
426 across multiple studies indicate the widespread toxic effects of 6PPD-Q. Moving forward,
427 continuing to study metabolic changes in *C. elegans* will lead to a better understanding of
428 6PPD-Q's biological targets.

429
430 Table 1. Summary of 6PPD and 6PPD-Q effect on aquatic organisms, terrestrial organisms,
431 and humans. High effect level indicates mortality at concentrations <100 µg/L 6PPD or 6PPD-Q
432 with severe deformities, and organ dysfunction. Moderate effect level indicates mortality induced
433 at concentrations ≥100 µg/L 6PPD or 6PPD-Q, and/or physiological and behavioral impairment.
434 Low effect level indicates mild or nonlethal effects, and/or limited biological impacts. Effect
435 levels were determined based on the LC50 values, literature, and biological effects.⁵¹
436 *Differences in LC50 values are likely due to differences in experimental design.

Deleted: This raises concerns that these tire pollutants may be passing from parent to child. Currently, there are no regulations for acceptable daily intake (ADI) or tolerable daily intake (TDI) for 6PPD or 6PPD-Q. More studies encompassing dust exposure, human excretions, co-exposure with other toxicants, and transgenerational transmission will give greater insight on exposure level so tolerance can be established. ¶

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Deleted: *Caenorhabditis elegans* (*C. elegans*) offer unique insight upon 6PPD-Q exposure as they are often terrestrial, but can also be found in aquatic environments. Investigating mortality in nematodes revealed only a 5 percent mortality rate when subjected to 100 µg/L 6PPD-Q (Table 1). It was noted that the mortality level was nowhere near complete sample mortality but was still significant when compared to the control group. Though mortality is uncommon in *C. elegans*, three studies found 6PPD-Q exposure resulted in a decreased lifespan. ¶ Like zebrafish, behavioral changes also appear in *C. elegans*. Two studies found treatment of lower 6PPD-Q concentrations ranging from 0.1 to 10 µg/L resulted in decreased and abnormal locomotion. Decreased locomotion was hypothesized to be caused by the neurodegeneration observed in D-type neurons following exposure to 10 µg/L 6PPD-Q. Neurodegeneration was also observed in dopaminergic, glutamatergic, serotonergic, and GABAergic neurons causing decreased sensory perception and neurotransmission. Comparatively, exposure to 1 to 10 µg/L 6PPD-Q resulted in a decrease of dopamine synthesis leading to a decrease of dopamine related behavior. Therefore, 6PPD-Q seems to be a neurotoxin, targeting a multitude of neurons and inhibiting normal behavior. ¶ No morphological changes were indicated in any *C. elegans* studies, however, metabolic and inflammatory responses were prevalent. Increased intestinal permeability was found in nematodes exposed to 1 to 10 µg/L 6-PPD-Q. Metabolism appears to be broadly affected as an increase in fatty acid synthesis res... [4]

	Chemical treated	LC50	Effect Level	Biological Effects	Findings	References
Coho Salmon	6PPD-Q	Embryonic 7.22 µg/L Juvenile* 0.79 µg/L, 41.0 ng/L, 95 ng/L Adult 100 mg/L	High	Mortality, morphological, physiological	Decreased size, increased hematocrit	[3,5,33,34]
Zebra fish	6PPD and 6PPD-Q	96 hr LC50 6PPD-Q of 132.92 µg/L, 96 hr LC50 6PPD of 442.62 µg/L and 2.2 mg/L, 120 hr LC50 6PPD of 0.87 mg/L*	Moderate	Mortality, Morphological, physiological	Decreased eye size, hatchability, body length and swim bladder, decreased swimming and phototactic response, increased sleeping, altered heart rate, cardiac output, oxygen consumption, and hormone and neurotransmitters	[8,10,13,14,16,18]
Brook Trout	6PPD-Q	Fry = 0.2 µg/L Fingerlings = 0.5 mg/L	High	Acute mortality, physiological	Increased interlamellar cell mass (ILCM) size, hematocrit, blood glucose, and total CO ₂ . Decreased blood sodium and chloride concentration	[52]
Rainbow Trout	6PPD-Q	1.00 µg/L and 2.08 µg/L*	High	Acute mortality, physiological	Increased cardiorespiration, respiration, and metabolism	[53,54]
Arctic Char	6PPD-Q	N/A	Low	Physiological	Increased metabolism	[53]
Lake Trout	6PPD-Q	96 hr = 0.50 µg/L	High	Acute mortality, morphological	Caudal fin and eye deformities	[55]

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Mice	6PPD and 6PPD-Q	N/A	Moderate	Physiological	Decreased testosterone, sperm quality, altered spermatogenesis, and sphingolipid metabolism pathways. Increased inflammation and lipid accumulation	[36–40]
Humans	6PPD and 6PPD-Q	N/A	Moderate	Physiological	Decreased BMI, altered gut microbiome, and increased susceptibility to illnesses	[19,20,24–26]
C. Elegans	6PPD-Q	100 µg/L	Moderate	Moderate lethality, behavioral, physiological	Altered locomotion, increased intestinal permeability, neurodegeneration, lipid accumulation and glycogen metabolism. Decreased glucose metabolism and dopamine synthesis	[42–50,56–58]

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4. Mechanistic Research for PPDs

5.1 PPDs and Metabolic Fate

The complete metabolism of 6PPD and 6PPD-Q is still largely unknown. However, several studies have identified cytochrome p450 enzymes, CYP1A, CYP3A, 3A4, and 2C19, as integral to the metabolic breakdown of 6PPD and 6PPD-Q.^{21,22,59} When CYP1A was inhibited by α -naphthoflavone (ANF) and quercetin, the levels of unmetabolised 6PPD-Q increased, indicating its enzymatic activity is imperative.²²

There still remains a need to identify transformation products (TPs) as potential biomarkers. Of the many papers discussed below, the main focus was that of PPDs and how they interact with metabolic proteins focusing on the short biological half-life of the toxicants. PPDs have been studied in in vivo and in vitro models including zebrafish, mice, human and rat liver microsomes, rainbow trout liver cells (RTL-W1), and human liver cell lines (L02 and HepG2).^{7,12,21–23,60} For example, the half-life of 6PPD-Q was studied in mice blood, urine, and feces (5.32, 6.20, and 3.87 hours respectively).²³ When studying transformation products of toxicants, typically transformations are labeled as Phase I and Phase II metabolites with subsequent modifications. Across species, the TPs may vary depending on the metabolic pathways used to detoxify 6PPD and 6PPD-Q. Two transformations of 6PPD-Q, hydroxylation, being the most commonly reported, and glucuronidation, have been identified across species as

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metabolites.^{7,12,21,23,60,61} Thorough research has indicated strong potential for hydroxylation and glucuronidation TPs to act as effective biomarkers for 6PPD-Q exposure, further investigation is needed to identify possible biomarkers for 6PPD's metabolism.

5.2 PPDs and Protein Interactions

The metabolic breakdown and widespread protein interactions of 6PPD and 6PPD-Q complicate our full understanding of their toxicological implications. Solidifying metabolic biomarkers for both PPDs is the first step towards understanding how these toxicants interact *in vivo* and *in vitro*. PPDs have been reported to interact with proteins affiliated with blood, neurons, and cancer. Molecular docking has shown 6PPD and 6PPD-Q forms complexes with human serum albumin (HSA), alters the secondary structure, and differentially affects the esterase activity.⁶² 6PPD-Q has also been shown to interact with neuronal proteins involved in neurotransmitter reception and synthesis, for example BAS-1, GLB-10, and acetylcholinesterase.^{46,47,63} These interactions are likely the basis for the neurotoxicity seen in the presence of 6PPD-Q. Molecular docking has also uncovered 6PPD-Q's potential effect on prostate cancer signaling pathway proteins. Normally, JAK2 is involved in regulating the cell cycle, but since it has strong binding affinity with 6PPD-Q, this has implications regarding the metastasis of prostate cancer.⁶⁴ Seeing that both PPDs have a high likelihood of interacting with a broad range of proteins, uncovering the full scope of these interactions is key to piecing together the toxicology picture.

5. PPDs and Gene Regulation Related to the Immune Response 6.1 Gene Regulation Prior to the Inflammatory Response

Current research indicates a trend in 6PPD and 6PPD-Q's proclivity to prompt an organism's immune response, primarily via the organism's inflammation pathway. We aim to distinguish differences in an organism's gene regulation seen leading up to, during, and after the inflammatory response. This area of research is particularly rich, though recent publications indicate a need to map what is currently known across species in terms of the immune response (Figure 3).

Prior to inducing an inflammatory response, PPDs create a stressful environment that results in cellular oxidative damage. This is characterized by an elevation of ROS levels. Many studies directly measured ROS levels following 6PPD treatment and found an increase in ROS in embryonic, larval, and adult zebrafish.^{11,12,65-68} In comparison, 6PPD-Q was found to induce oxidative stress within human liver cell lines, like L02 and HepG2, as well as in *C. elegans* and mice.^{22,37,41,47,69,70}

To further confirm the presence of increased ROS following PPD treatment, researchers have analyzed the regulation of antioxidant genes responsible for mediating oxidative stress like SOD-2, SOD-3, and SOD-4. Two studies found increased expression of antioxidant genes, further indicating oxidative stress is caused by PPDs.^{41,63} *C. elegans*, tend to employ the mitochondrial unfolded protein response (mt UPR) in the presence of oxidative stress. Specifically, this response is mediated by set-6, met-2, jmjd-1.2, and jmjd-3.1. These genes were dysregulated in the presence of 6PPD-Q, thereby hindering the mt UPR response and increasing *C. elegans*' susceptibility to oxidative damage.^{71,72} Consistent exposure to PPDs may prolong the stressful cellular conditions causing continued ROS production. ROS then act as signaling molecules launching an inflammation response.⁷³

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The metabolic fate of 6PPD and 6PPD-Q is still largely unknown. PPDs have been studied *in vivo* and *in vitro* models including zebrafish, mice, human and rat liver microsomes, rainbow trout liver cells (RTL-W1), and human liver cell lines (L02 and HepG2). A short half-life of a toxicant showcases the need to identify potential biomarkers in the transformation products (TPs). For example in mice, the half-life of 6PPD-Q in blood, urine, and feces were identified to be 5.32, 6.20, and 3.87 hours respectively. When studying transformation products of toxicants, typically transformations are labeled as Phase I and Phase II metabolites with subsequent modifications. Across species, the TPs may vary depending on the metabolic pathways used to detoxify 6PPD and 6PPD-Q. Two transformations of 6PPD-Q, hydroxylation and glucuronidation, have been identified across species as common metabolites. Likewise, the most common transformation of 6PPD is hydroxylation. Thorough research has indicated strong potential for hydroxylation and glucuronidation TPs to act as effective biomarkers for 6PPD-Q exposure, further investigation is needed to identify possible biomarkers for 6PPD's metabolism.¶

Several studies have identified cytochrome p450 enzymes, CYP1A, CYP3A, 3A4, and 2C19, as integral to the metabolic breakdown of 6PPD and 6PPD-Q. When CYP1A was inhibited by α -naphthoflavone (ANF) and quercetin, the levels of unmetabolised 6PPD-Q increased, indicating its enzymatic activity is imperative. Beyond interacting with metabolic enzymes, PPDs also interact with proteins affiliated with blood, neurons, and cancer. Molecular docking has confirmed 6PPD and 6PPD-Q forms complexes with human serum albumin (HSA), alters the secondary structure, and differentially affects the esterase activity. 6PPD-Q has also been shown to interact with neuronal proteins involved in neurotransmitter reception and synthesis, for example BAS-1, GLB-10, and acetylcholinesterase. These interactions are likely the basis for the neurotoxicity seen in the presence of 6PPD-Q. Molecular docking has also uncovered 6PPD-Q's potential effect on prostate cancer signaling pathway proteins. Normally, JAK2 is involved in regulating the cell cycle, but since it has strong binding affinity with 6PPD-Q, this has implications regarding the metastasis of prostate cancer. Taken together, the metabolic breakdown and widespread protein interactions of 6PPD and 6PPD-Q complicate our full understanding of their toxicological implications. We believe not addressing these complications may prevent progress in policy making. As stated, solidifying metabolic biomarkers for both PPDs is the first step (... [5])

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699 **6.2 Gene Regulation During the Inflammatory Response** How do PPDs affect
 700 **gene regulation of the inflammatory response?**

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701 After consistent PPD exposure elevates ROS, an inflammatory response is generated by
 702 the upregulation of proinflammatory genes. These genes code for cytokines which activate the
 703 immune response and participate in their own positive feedback mechanism.^{72,74} Classifications
 704 for cytokines include tumor necrosis factors, interleukins, and chemokines.⁷⁵

705 In mice, zebrafish, and human lung and endometrial epithelial cells, 6PPD exposure
 706 most notably appeared to cause gene dysregulation of cytokines TNF α .^{35,66,76,77} Upregulation of
 707 TNF α implies the propagation of inflammation pathways NF-k β and MAPK. NF-k β helps to
 708 mediate aspects of innate and adaptive immunity while also creating a positive feedback loop by
 709 proliferating further waves of cytokines (Table 2).⁷⁸ With cytokines' ability to create a positive
 710 feedback loop, chronic inflammation is possible.

711 Gene dysregulation of cytokines following 6PPD-Q exposure has been analyzed more
 712 thoroughly in coho salmon, mice, and humans.^{5,36,37,66} Similar to organisms exposed to 6PPD,
 713 the quinone derivative also caused an upregulation of cytokine TNF α . Again confirming
 714 activation of the NF-k β and MAPK pathways. 6PPD-Q also upregulated the expression of
 715 cytokines IL-6, Ripk1, and Fadd indicating JAK-STAT, necrosis, and apoptosis may also be
 716 prompted. Additionally, this has been shown to further disrupt genes regulating metabolism of
 717 macromolecules.

718 **6.3 Gene Regulation Following the Inflammatory Response** 6PPD exposure
 719

720 has been well documented to dysregulate lipid metabolism in zebrafish. Multiple studies find an
 721 increased expression of genes regulating fatty acid synthesis, like *ppary* and *fasn-1*, while there
 722 was a decreased expression of genes regulating β -oxidation like *acs-2* and *ech-2*.^{61,77,79,80}
 723 Dysregulation of lipid metabolism was further evidenced by an increase in triglyceride and
 724 cholesterol levels. In studies treating zebrafish and *C. elegans* with 6PPD-Q, upregulated lipid
 725 synthesis and downregulated β -oxidation were also prevalent.^{15,49}

726 Though there is evidence of other biomolecules, like glucose, with disrupted metabolism,
 727 lipids have been by far the most studied.⁵⁹ Consequences may extend beyond gene
 728 dysregulation of lipids following continued PPD exposure. As mentioned before, following three
 729 weeks of 6PPD-Q exposure, mice displayed disrupted lipid metabolism which culminated in fatty
 730 liver disease.³⁹ For aquatic organisms known to experience long term exposure of the tire
 731 pollutants, this raises a serious risk of hepatotoxicity. Long term damage to the liver may further
 732 exacerbate the inflammatory response already prompted by the cellular stress of PPDs.

Deleted: Studies have looked at gene dysregulation of cytokines following 6PPD exposure in mice, zebrafish, and human lung and endometrial epithelial cells. An upregulation of TNF α confirmed 6PPD causes propagation of the NF-k β and MAPK inflammation pathways was found. Studies also analyzed gene dysregulation of cytokines following 6PPD-Q exposure in coho salmon, mice, and humans. A more comprehensive list of dysregulated cytokines and inflammatory pathways were amassed. Similar to organisms treated with 6PPD, 6PPD-Q also caused an upregulation of cytokine TNF α again confirming activation of the NF-k β and MAPK pathways. Upregulated expression of other cytokines like IL-6, Ripk1, and Fadd indicate JAK-STAT, necrosis, and apoptosis are also prompted. Furthermore, cytokines' ability to create a positive feedback loop may induce chronic inflammation. This has been shown to further disrupt genes regulating metabolism of macromolecules

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 734
 735 Table 2. Gene and protein dysregulation in coho salmon, zebrafish, mice, *C. elegans*, and
 736 endometrial epithelial cells and their morphological effects.

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	Chemical treated	Genes and proteins dysregulated	Alterations to
Coho Salmon	0.1-7.2 μ g/L 6PPD-Q	TNF α , il1 β , JAM, and ifny	Blood brain barrier, vascular permeability, and inflammation
Zebrafish	2.2 mg/L 6PPD and 0.25-25 μ g/L 6PPD-Q	<i>rpe65a</i> , <i>opn1lw1</i> , <i>per1a</i> , <i>per3</i> , and <i>cry3a</i>	Thyroid signaling pathway, eye development, estrogen signaling and circadian rhythm

Mice	10-100 mg/kg 6PPD and 6PPD-Q	Ripk1, Fadd, Il-6st, and Il-16	Immune system, macrophage infiltration, and prostate cancer activation
Endometrial epithelial cells	1-10 μ M 6PPD and 1 μ M 6PPD-Q	TNF α , IL6, and TGF β 1	Endometrial receptivity and inflammatory responses
C. elegans	10 μ g/L 6PPD-Q	atfs-1, ubl-5, dve-1 fasn-1, and pod-2	Mitochondrial unfolded protein response and lipid accumulation

759 Figure 3. Comprehensive overview of known interactions of 6PPD and 6PPD-Q (created using
760 BioRender.com).
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763 **7. Recommendations in PPD Research** Through this literature search we aimed to
764 summarize the toxicological effects of PPDs, 6PPD and 6PPD-Q, on aquatic and terrestrial
765 organisms and point out the major gaps that need to be addressed as regulations are
766 developed. After compiling data covering *in vivo* and *in vitro* models, it is clear that 6PPD and
767 6PPD-Q have some overlapping toxic effects but also some distinct characteristics. Throughout
768 our commentary we discussed progressional life stages for coho salmon and zebrafish. We
769 believe a good foundation has been laid outlining the lifecycle effects. While this area of study is
770 still important, we think it can be deprioritized moving forward in the PPD research field. Instead,
771 integrating interdisciplinary research methods will help increase knowledge and help inform
772 global regulations (Figure 4). We specifically recommend focusing on discerning the toxic
773 mechanisms of 6PPD and 6PPD-Q through the following routes:

774 **7.1 Transgenerational studies.** A considerable amount of research has been published
775 covering lifecycle effects of PPDs, however there remains a noticeable absence of
776

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Deleted: Because the discovery of PPDs as an environmental toxicant is relatively new, integrating interdisciplinary research methods will help increase knowledge and help inform global regulations. We specifically recommend focusing on discerning the toxic mechanisms of 6PPD and 6PPD-Q through the following routes:

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786 research establishing the inheritance of epigenetic changes and mutations. Given that
787 some species are evidenced to be more tolerant to 6PPD and 6PPD-Q, we expect to
788 see a similar trend of toxic effects in future generations. To remedy this, employing
789 multiple generational studies focusing on epigenetic changes will give key insights to the
790 long term repercussions of PPD usage.

791 **7.2 Female model organisms.** As of now, the majority of rodent toxicology studies have
792 explored the effects of 6PPD-Q on the male mouse model finding defects in the process
793 of spermatogenesis. While these discoveries are highly relevant, uncovering the effects
794 on female reproduction are of equal importance. To bridge this gap, we recommend
795 implementing female rodent studies in parallel to the already completed male rodent
796 studies. Furthermore, including both male and female models in studies will ensure
797 parallel information is being reported.

799 1. **7.3 Fungal cell toxicology and metagenomics.** Fungi are an integral aspect of water
800 ecosystems. Fungal communities give vital information about the health of the
801 ecosystem they reside in. No studies have ventured into the effects of PPDs on fungal
802 cells. This could be an interesting approach to discern effects of 6PPD and 6PPD-Q. As
803 fungal cells are single-celled eukaryotes, cell trafficking and protein interactions can
804 easily be studied. Implementation of yeast studies opens the door to faster turnaround of
805 data acquisition as well as multi-faceted research approaches, such as metabolomics,
806 metagenomics, transcriptomics, and bioaccumulation.

807 **7.4 Fate of metabolites and their interactions in vivo.** A preliminary foundation of
808 6PPD and 6PPD-Q metabolites has been formed. However, many metabolites have
809 been identified, as either Phase I or Phase II, but the research has stalled there. The
810 continued breakdown mechanisms and pathways of transformation products is important
811 in identifying all exposure biomarkers. We suggest implementing high performance liquid
812 chromatography coupled with mass spectrometry into metabolite studies at various life
813 stages. Ultimately, uncovering the pathways used to metabolize 6PPD and 6PPD-Q will
814 aid in our understanding of their mechanistic impact and identify screenable biomarkers.

815 **7.5 PPD effects on cancer cell lines.** Using cancer cells as a model system is useful
816 because of the ease of culturing and wide availability. Since cancerous cell lines are
817 immortalized, making long term studies investigating toxicological effects of PPDs
818 possible. Currently, there is an insufficient amount of research investigating how PPDs
819 interact with cellular components. To build upon current findings, studies should
820 investigate effects on cell viability, apoptosis, and ROS formation in additional cell lines
821 following PPD treatment. We also suggest pivoting towards studies evaluating ATP
822 production, lipid peroxidation, and cell trafficking. Implementing these assessments is
823 essential to uncovering the mechanisms behind PPD toxicity and serve as a good path
824 to uncovering metabolic fate.

825 **7.6 Single-cell sequencing (SCS).** Single-cell sequencing has many advantages such
826 as uncovering discrepancies in cell population responses, pinpointing exact toxicity
827 limits, and providing insight into dynamic cellular responses. There has been an effort to
828 perform bulk sequencing especially for transcriptomic studies. However, these types of
829 experiments can sometimes lose the nuanced responses from individual cells within a
830 population. Implementing this technique into PPD toxicology studies may help reveal
831 novel information like sensitivity limits, how different cell types, and organ systems
832 respond to PPD exposure.

Deleted: As seen with coho salmon, the tolerance level, although small, increased throughout the lifecycle. Determining lifecycle tolerance differences for robust species, sensitive species, and any in between will help environmentalists be well informed when implementing PPD regulations for various habitats. ¶

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Deleted: <#>Epigenetics. Another route to address transgenerational research gaps is epigenetic studies. This field gives insight into gene alterations at the individual level as well as possible explanations for inheritance of mutations and exposure impacts. ¶

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Deleted: We discussed various studies using different model organisms and cell lines showing toxic ef (... [7])

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7.7 Coexposure of environmental toxicants. 6PPD and 6PPD-Q are not isolated toxicants. The likelihood of multiple toxic chemicals, like PHAs and metaloids, interacting with PPDs is high. Limited information has been published encompassing coexposure in humans. We specifically note that there have not been any coexposure studies conducted using coho salmon. Investigating coexposure of PPDs with other prominent environmental toxicants in as many model organisms as possible would give insightful information on how different toxicants interact synergistically, antagonistically, or not at all. Additionally, any interactions that are discovered will only bolster the scientific evidence needed to implement strict regulations of PPDs.

All the above-mentioned future research trends are equally important in advancing scientific understanding of 6PPD and 6PPD-Q. Collectively, each area of emphasis will bridge the gaps in knowledge and provide a more thorough understanding of tire pollutant impacts. Eventually, this ground-breaking research will help formulate regulations and combat the toxic effects of PPDs.

Author Contributions

E.B.: writing-original draft preparation, review, editing; M.M.: writing-original draft preparation, review, editing; K.K.: review, editing, and supervision. All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

Funding statement

This work was supported by Missouri State University's thesis funds to Emma Braun and Roy Blunt Endowed Professorship funds to Kyoungtae Kim.

Disclosure of interest

The authors report there are no competing interests to declare.

Data Availability Statement

Data sharing is not applicable as no new data was created or analyzed in this review.

Acknowledgements

We thank Missouri State University for funding and technology usage. We are grateful to the Kim lab members and faculty at Missouri State University for their insight and support. Lastly, we thank Kyoungtae Kim for his guidance during the writing process. Writing this review would not have been possible without his expertise.

Abbreviations

- 6PPD: (N-(1,3-dimethylbutyl)-N'-phenyl-p-phenylenediamine)
6PPD-Q: N-(1,3-dimethylbutyl)-N'-phenyl-p-phenylenediamine-quinone
USEPA: United States Environmental Protection agency
PPD: p-Phenylenediamine
CEPA: Canadian Environmental Protection Agency

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Deleted: Figure 4. Summary of future trends in 6PPD and 6PPD-Q studies (created using BioRender.com).

941 REACH: Registration, Evaluation, Authorisation and Restriction of Chemicals
942 NIH: National Institute of Health
943 LC50: Lethal concentration 50
944 UPLC-QE: Ultra performance liquid chromatography - Q Exactive Focus Orbitrap mass
945 spectrometry
946 BPM: beats per minute
947 IVF: *in vitro* fertilization
948 TNF α : Tumor Necrosis Factor - α
949 IL-1: Interleukin-1
950 IL-10: Interleukin-10
951 IL-6: Interleukin-6
952 *Il1b*: interleukin 1 *b* gene
953 *per1a*: Period circadian clock 1 a gene
954 *per3*: period circadian regulator 3
955 *cry3a*: cryptochrome circadian regulator 3a
956 Ripk1: Receptor-interacting serine/threonine-protein kinase 1
957 Fadd: Fas-associated death domain
958 Il-6st: Interleukin 6 Cytokine Family Signal Transducer
959 Il-16: Interleukin-16
960 *SOD-2*: superoxide dismutase 2 gene
961 *SOD-3*: superoxide dismutase 3 gene
962 *SOD-4*: superoxide dismutase 4 gene
963 ROS: Reactive oxygen species
964 MASLD: metabolic dysfunction-associated steatotic liver disease
965 BMI: Body mass index
966 PBDE: polybrominated diphenyl ethers
967 PCB: polychlorinated biphenyls

968 Ni: Nickel
969 Cu: Copper
970 ADI: acceptable daily intake
971 TDI: tolerable daily intake
972 ILCM: interlamellar cell mass
973 L02: human liver hepatocyte
974 HepG2: Hepatocellular carcinoma
975 TP: transformation product
976 Mt UPR: mitochondrial unfold protein response
977 *atfs-1*: Activating Transcription Factor associated with Stress-1
978 *ubl-5*: ubiquitin-like protein 5
979 *dve-1*: homeobox transcriptional regulator
980 *fasn-1*: Fatty acid synthase 1 gene
981 *pod-2*: Acetyl-CoA Carboxylase gene
982 p450: cytochrome p450 protein
983 CYP1A2: Cytochrome p450 1A2
984 CYP3A: Cytochrome p450 3A
985 2C19: Cytochrome p450 2C19
986 ANF: α -naphthoflavone
987 BAS-1: cytochrome p450 superfamily protein
988 GRB-10: globin like protein 10
989 JAK2: Janus kinase 2
990 SOD: superoxide dismutase
991 HSA: Human Serum Albumin
992 NF- κ B: Nuclear factor kappa-light-chain-enhancer of activated B cells
993 PAH: polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons

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995 **References**

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1398 **Supplemental Information**

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Supplemental Figure 1. World map detailing locations that have detected 6PPD and 6PPD-Q (created using Biorender.com).

Supplemental Table 1. Countries with 6PPD and/or 6PPD-Q detected in local samples.

Country	Location of Sample Site	Chemical	References
Argentina	Buenos Aires	6PPD-Q	[⁸¹]
Australia	Queensland (Brisbane River)	6PPD-Q	[^{82,83}]
Brazil	São Paulo	6PPD-Q	[⁸¹]
Canada	Southern Ontario (Don River and Highland Creek) and Toronto	6PPD-Q	[^{81,84–86}]
Chile	Santiago	6PPD-Q	[⁸¹]
China	Guangzhou (Liuxi River and Guanghua Basin), South China (Greater Bay Area), Guangdong (Pearl River and Dongjiang river), Zhejiang (Zhujiang river and Jiaojiang River), Yangtze River, Taiyuan, Zhengzhou, Shanghai, Nanjing, Hangzhou, and Hong Kong	6PPD and 6PPD-Q	[^{19,87–99}]
Colombia	Bogota	6PPD-Q	[⁸¹]
Germany	Leipzig Saxony	6PPD and 6PPD-Q	[^{100–103}]

India	Kolkata and New Delhi	6PPD-Q	[⁸¹]
Japan	Tokyo	6PPD-Q	[^{81,104}]
Nigeria	Lagos	6PPD-Q	[⁸¹]
Poland	Warsaw	6PPD-Q	[⁸¹]
Spain	Madrid	6PPD-Q	[⁸¹]
USA	California (San Francisco Bay), Colorado, Georgia, Kansas, Michigan, Minnesota, Mississippi (Oxford), New York, North Carolina, Oklahoma, Oregon, Texas, Virginia, and Washington (Tacoma)	6PPD-Q	[¹⁰⁵⁻¹⁰⁹]

1404 Supplemental Table 2. Common concentrations of 6PPD* and 6PPD-Q* listed as micrograms
1405 per liter ($\mu\text{g/L}$) and corresponding conversion to nanomolar (nM).

6PPD ($\mu\text{g/L}$)	6PPD (nM)	6PPD-Q ($\mu\text{g/L}$)	6PPD-Q (nM)
0.1	0.370	0.1	0.340
5	1.86	5	1.68
10	3.73	10	3.35
50	18.6	50	16.8
100	37.3	100	33.5
500	186	500	167.6
1000	373	1000	335

1406 *Based on molar masses 6PPD, 268.4 g/mol and 6PPD-Q, 298.4 g/mol
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